

Organometallic Chemistry — Challenges and Opportunities

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Manuscript received 24 November 1993, revised 26 October 1994, accepted 2 March 1995

Organometallic chemistry, starting as a branch of organic chemistry later incorporated coordination chemistry and has developed into a true multidisciplinary science. It is not only acting as a bridge between the two conventional branches of chemistry—inorganic and organic, but is also assuming tremendous importance from the point of view of industrial, biological and environmental aspects. It satisfies several social needs and is a challenging science with a great future potential and unlimited opportunities. To realise these expectations, greater emphasis has to be laid on the learning of organometallic chemistry in a comprehensive manner at the undergraduate, postgraduate as well as the research levels.

Compounds containing at least one direct metal to carbon bond are termed as 'organometallic'. This bond may be either a σ - or a π -bond. Initially a domain of the traditional sub-field of organic chemistry, it has now attained the status of a vast and burgeoning field and is tending towards a distinct discipline by itself full of excitement and activity, with inherent surprises and challenges. This is an area where a rich harvest of new and previously undreamed of structural types is reaped every year through an unusual number of chance discoveries and totally unsuspected reactions in addition to elegant and skilful synthetic programmes. The combination of efforts of synthetic, structural and theoretical chemists as well as kineticists has provided an invaluable underlying rationale for various aspects of this continually evolving field. The industrial chemists have also exploited and extended the results by developing several catalytic processes of immense importance. Thus, the field of organometallic chemistry is continuing to grow into a thriving area that spans interesting new types of reactions, unusual structures and practical applications in organic synthesis and industrial catalysis. These provide obviously strong challenges and hence unlimited opportunities. New challenges arise in scientific fields from 'pushes and pulls'¹. The pull comes from the desire to address societal needs and the push from advances in science and technology which include, among others the phenomenal growth in and availability of modern instrumentation, significant developments in synthetic strategies, a major growth in theory which enables one to calculate the electronic and geometric structures in the ground and excited states and a much greater understanding of factors controlling the stabilities of molecules and their dynamics. It is the intention of this article to transfer this excitement of great advances made in the area of organometallic chemistry to its readers such that the challenges can be met and the opportunities seized effectively for its further phenomenal growth.

We will briefly discuss some important types of organometallic compounds and also highlight precisely the ways in which they can satisfy the societal needs. It is felt appropriate and instructive to discuss briefly some of the

selected landmarks in the historical development of the subject as looking at the past may help to predict the prospects of the field and not to ignore the embryonic fields. Indeed, from small embers great fires may grow! Detailed authoritative account of the history is available elsewhere²⁻⁸.

Brief historical background

Although cacodyl oxide, $[\text{Me}_2\text{As}]_2\text{O}$, was discovered as early as 1760, the first organometallic compound recorded is a platinum-complex, $\text{K}[\text{PtCl}_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)]$, reported by a Danish pharmacist Zeise in 1827, whose bonding properties were explained a century later. While trying to establish the presence of organic radicals, Frankland⁹, the discoverer of helium, accidentally discovered ethyl/zinc containing a direct metal-to-alkyl σ -bond. He then prepared the important alkylmercury compound, Me_2Hg and additionally, Et_4Sn and Me_3B . The first binary (homoleptic) metal carbonyl, $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$, was reported by Mond¹⁰, the founder of the Imperial Chemical Industries, England, in 1890 and Grignard's reagents were synthesised in 1900¹¹. The first σ -organotransition metal compound, Me_3PtI , was reported in 1909 by W. J. Pope and polyphenylchromium compounds in 1919 by F. Hein. In 1929 F. A. Paneth generated alkyl radicals through pyrolysis of PbR_4 , and a year earlier W. Hieber inaugurated his systematic study of metal carbonyls. The Fischer-Tropsch process¹², a heterogeneously catalysed reaction was discovered in 1925 leading to the commercialisation of the process for making liquid hydrocarbons from coal-derived 'synthesis gas'. From 1951 onwards, developments in the field of organotransition metal chemistry were rather rapid. The discovery of ferrocene¹³⁻¹⁶ in 1951 and the invention of the Ziegler process¹⁷ in 1953 are considered as two most important landmarks triggering the advent of a new era. Ferrocene was proposed to have a sandwich-bonded structure where the two planar cyclopentadienyl ligands symmetrically bind the central iron atom. The correctness of this proposal was quickly established with the aid of infrared and nmr spectroscopy and later by X-ray crystallography. The discovery of ferrocene together with the invention of the Ziegler pro-

cess triggered the explosive growth of organotransition metal chemistry.

The revolutionary novel process for converting ethylene into polyethylene by a catalyst composed of TiCl_4 and AlEt_3 was invented by Ziegler¹⁷ in Germany and the process was transferred to Natta's group in Italy, where processes for the polymerisation of propylene, butadiene and isoprene were developed quite rapidly¹⁸. This is a striking example of how basic research on organometallic compounds, regarded as curiosities at that time, suddenly produced a worldwide industrial process proving the application of organometallic chemistry. Ziegler and Natta in 1963 and Wilkinson and Fischer in 1973 were awarded Nobel prizes. The discovery of the Ziegler process was followed by the Wacker process for converting ethylene into acetaldehyde¹⁹. Both the processes had a profound impact on the rapidly developing petrochemical industry at that time. On the other hand, a variety of exciting compounds were discovered in the academic field in quick succession. Among them the Vaska's complex²⁰, the carbene and the carbyne complexes^{21,22} and dinitrogen complexes²³, to name a few, have evoked considerable interest. Organometallic compounds of alkali metals, alkaline earths, aluminium, boron, mercury, tin, lead, silicon and other metals have also been developed, studied and utilised for the benefit of society. The organoboron and organophosphorus compounds have proved to be much more versatile and of greater utility than Grignard and organolithium reagents in organic synthesis. The utility of organometallics in chemotherapy realised in the early 20th century has received continued attention. The discovery of vitamin B₁₂ (containing a cobalt-carbon bond) has evoked renewed interest in bioorganometallic chemistry which has taken a new turn in the second half of the present century with the increasing awareness of the environmental aspects of metal-carbon bonded compounds. This problem is in some cases assuming serious dimensions in view of the large scale utilisation of organometallics as biocides and in various industries, calling for caution in the unrestricted use of materials like lead alkyls as oil additives. It will be appropriate here to mention the necessity of single-minded devotion and determination in any field of activity. It took eight years for Crowfoot-Hodgkins²⁴ to establish the structure of vitamin B₁₂ through her desperately time-consum-

ing and laborious work, and once this was established, Woodward who had succeeded in the total synthesis of many complicated molecules (e.g. chlorophyll, quinine, cholesterol, strychnine and reserpine) was determined to attempt the synthesis of coenzyme B₁₂ that had many chiral centres. It was a tough job for him and the total synthesis of vitamin B₁₂ was achieved in 1972 with the collaboration of Eschenmoser in Switzerland. It required 65–70 synthetic steps resulting from the efforts of 99 chemists in 11 years²⁵. A Herculean task indeed!

Classification of organometallic compounds

Both main group and transition metals form organometallic compounds with direct M–C bonds. While M–C σ -bonded compounds are well-known for both non-transition and transition metals it is unique for transition metals to form M–C π -bonds. The transition metal-carbon multiple bonded compounds are of two types: those in high oxidation states (e.g. alkylidene and alkylidyne complexes) and those in low oxidation states (e.g. carbene and carbyne complexes). Indeed, depending on the nature of the attached groups, the metal-carbon bond may be single (M–C), double (M=C) or triple (M $\equiv$ C) maintaining the tetravalency of carbon (Chart 1). An unusual organotransition metal compound is the structurally characterised tungsten complex 1²⁶, which manifests within the same molecule metal-carbon single, double, and triple bonds exhibiting a range of W–C bond lengths (2.258, 1.842 and 1.785 Å respectively).

Chart 1

It was Fischer who prepared the first transition metal-carbene complex in 1964²¹ and the first carbyne complex containing the metal-carbon triple bond in 1973²⁷. These were regarded as structural curiosities for some time, but it was soon realised that carbene complexes are active cata-

lysts for olefin metathesis and the carbyne complexes can catalyse the acetylene metathesis²⁸. The present author while spending some time in the Technical University, Munich, Germany, had the opportunity of listening to the thrilling as well as stimulating lectures of Fischer and discussing with him about the sandwich complexes and his later discoveries, the multiply bonded metal-carbon compounds—the carbenes and the carbynes.

The now famous sandwich complex ferrocene, $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$, is the forerunner of a wide variety of compounds of carbocyclic ligands with transition metals. The prefix hapto is proposed to designate the number of carbon atoms bonded to the metal. Thus, ferrocene is formally named as bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)iron(II), where η^5 - is called pentahapto. Examples of η^2 -, η^3 - and η^4 -ligands are the olefins, π -allyl and cyclobutadiene respectively, with bonding through 2, 3 or 4 carbon atoms to the metal. The series of mixed sandwich complexes (4–8) containing various carbocyclic ligands apart from η^5 -cyclopentadienyl demonstrate examples of binding of η^3 -, η^4 -, η^5 -, η^6 - and η^7 -ligands. The cyclopentadienyl ligand can sometimes act as a mono-hapto or tri-hapto ligand and the complex 9 is an unusual case that contains η^5 -, η^3 - and η^1 -cyclopentadienyl ligands. The complex 5 is rather exciting as cyclobutadiene was established to be a very reactive and unstable compound with a short life at room temperature and in 1956 Longuet-Higgins and Orgel proposed on the basis of MO considerations that this square-planar molecule would be stabilised when attached to transition metals. This prophecy was realised in 1959 by Criegee²⁹ by the synthesis of the first π -tetramethylcyclobutadiene complex. This is a convincing example of how theory precedes experiment!

Complexes of non-aromatic olefin and acetylene com-

plexes as well as those of dienes and the three-electron donor allyl group, $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-$ are known. The pioneer example is Zeise's salt $[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)\text{Cl}_3]^-$ where the ethylene occupies the fourth coordination site of the square-planar complex with the C–C axis perpendicular to the platinum-ligand plane. The simplest acetylene complexes resemble those of ethylene and there are analogues of Zeise's salt containing platinum(II), d^8 , and an acetylene molecule which occupies a position like that of ethylene in Zeise's salt. Some examples of the complexes with such types of linkages are shown in 10–18. Depending upon conditions, polynuclear complexes, e.g. 19 to 23 may be formed.

The magnitude of organometallic chemistry is truly immense; many new substances remain to be discovered. There are several metals and the number and variety of L_nM fragments that can be considered to construct organometallic complexes is exceedingly high. Fortunately, however, some very useful generalisation can be made by taking account the electronic structure of fragments. Thus, by using the isolobal analogy³⁰, it is possible to know the approximate number, shape and electron occupation of the frontier orbitals of almost any L_nM fragment, and with this information their bonding abilities can be estimated. Ac-

TABLE I—GENERAL ISOLOBAL RELATIONSHIPS

L_nM	d^n	CH_m
L_2M	10	CH_2
L_3M	9	CH
L_4M	8	CH_2
L_5M	7	CH_3
L_5M	6	CH_2
L_5M	5	CH
L_6M	5	CH_3
L_4M	9	CH_3
L_3M	10	CH_4

According to Hoffmann, two fragments are isolobal if the number, symmetry properties, approximate energy and shape of their frontier orbitals as well as the number of electrons occupying them are similar—not identical but similar. The isolobal connection allows a joint consideration of inorganic, organic and organometallic structures, the relationships being based on the isolobal nature of the respective molecular fragments. A great number of mononuclear organometallic complexes can be designed by realising that a fragment isolobal with CH_3 can combine with one of the $-\text{C}$ ligands, forming $\text{L}_n\text{M}(-\text{C})$; a fragment isolobal with CH_2 can combine with either two $-\text{C}$ ligands, forming $\text{L}_n\text{M}(-\text{C})_2$ or with one $=\text{C}$ ligand, forming $\text{L}_n\text{M}(=\text{C})$; and that a fragment isolobal with CH may combine with three $-\text{C}$, or with one $-\text{C}$ and one $=\text{C}$, or with one $\equiv\text{C}$, giving respectively, $\text{L}_n\text{M}(-\text{C})_3$, $\text{L}_n\text{M}(-\text{C})(=\text{C})$ and $\text{L}_n\text{M}(\equiv\text{C})$ (Chart 2).

Chart 2

Similar to the mononuclear complexes, it is possible to determine the types of carbon ligands that may be combined with a particular polymetal-ligand framework to form a polynuclear organometallic compound. The design of polynuclear organometallic compound is greatly complicated by the fact that C-C, M-C and M-M bonds may be distributed in various ways and, frequently, the real examples have a high degree of delocalisation and many electron deficient multicentre interactions, which are the aspects that depend on factors still not fully understood.

Synthesis of organometallic compounds

The procedures for the formation of bonds directly between metals and carbon are broadly through oxidative addition, exchange, insertion and elimination type of reactions which include direct synthesis, mixed-metal synthesis, transmetallation, metal exchange, metathesis, metal-halogen exchange, metallation, mercuration, hydrometallation, carbometallation, carbene insertion and decarboxylation etc. These will not be discussed further here and the interested readers may refer to several text-books and references²⁻⁶. Depending on the organometallic compound required to be synthesised, one or more of these methods or even more specialised techniques may be adopted. Various new synthetic methods utilising transition metal complexes have been developed. Multistep conventional synthetic approaches can sometimes be shortened

by using transition metal complexes, which promote reactions in good yields and with high regio- and stereochemical specificities.

Some applications of organometallic compounds

Organic synthesis :

Starting from the use of Grignard and organolithium reagents, the usefulness of organometallics as reagents for organic synthesis has been one of the most important aspects deserving attention. Organometallic compounds of alkali metals, alkaline earths, aluminium, boron, mercury, tin, lead, silicon, and other metals have been studied and employed for the benefit of society. Silicones, for example, used in lubricants, rubbers and surfactants, rank amongst the most useful commercial products. Organosilicon compounds, organoboron compounds, as well as organometallic compounds of other main-group metals such as aluminium and tin are attracting interest among synthetic organic chemists. The work of Brown on hydroboration of olefins, together with Wittig's work on organophosphorous compounds may be mentioned to illustrate the importance of the field. Indeed, the versatility of organoboranes has given them a unique place amongst the reagents in organic laboratory. There has been remarkable development in the utilisation of almost all types of organometallics in carrying out specialised reactions in organic synthesis. The importance of organocopper reagents in organic synthesis has grown considerably. The homocuprate derivatives (e.g. R_2CuLi and $\text{RR}'\text{CuLi}$) are more versatile than simple RCu . The reactions often occur in highly selective fashion, stereoselectively, regioselectively and chemoselectively. There are numerous synthetic organic applications in which the transition-metal compound is a stoichiometric reactant, and others in which it serves as a catalyst.

Catalysis :

The transition metal organometallic compounds have found increasing use as catalysts in a variety of synthetic processes, such as polymerisation, oligomerisation, hydroformylation and oxidation of alkenes and other unsaturated compounds. A vacant coordination site has been suggested as the single most important property of a homogeneous catalyst. Homogeneous catalysts are becoming increasingly important because of the high rates, dramatic substrate selectivities, and mild conditions which can be achieved by these systems. They are principally applied to the high-volume, low-cost 'commodity chemicals', such as plasticiser alcohols made by the oxo process and acetic acid derived by the carbonylation of methanol, and are likely to have important application in the manufacture of high-value 'fine chemicals', such as pharmaceuticals, perfumes, agricultural chemicals (e.g. herbicides and insecticides), and food additives (e.g. flavouring agents and sweeteners). An important example is the manufacture of L-Dopa

used for treatment of Parkinson's disease via catalytic hydrogenation, the catalyst being a soluble, chiral rhodium complex. Also using an organorhodium catalyst a plant capable of producing more than 10⁶ metric tonnes per year of acetic acid from methanol and carbon monoxide has recently gone on stream in Texas (the Monsanto process) :

This process is not only selective and high-yielding but is also very fast; the rates are in the enzymatic range. The process is superior to all other methods. The use of catalysts of the sort becomes increasingly important in a world facing shortages and high cost of petroleum, until recently the cheapest sources of both feedstocks and energy. The history of organic industrial chemistry can be organised around the relative reactivities of the organic feedstocks³¹. The period 1910–1950 can be characterised as the 'acetylene period' since readily available, highly reactive, but rather expensive acetylene was employed. With the contributions of Ziegler and Natta, the alkenes have predominated the scene since 1950 onwards. Homogeneously catalysed hydrogenation of organic substrates is an important class of organometallic reactions and olefins have been the most thoroughly studied substrates. Many familiar articles of commerce are derived from the carbon-carbon bond forming reactions associated with polymerisation and oligomerisation of olefins and acetylenes that are catalysed by transition metal compounds. For example, polyethylene and polypropylene are produced in huge quantities (several million tonnes per year) by these catalysts :

where M = transition metal; a = initiation, b = propagation and c = termination steps.

The transition-metal catalysed oligomerisation reactions of alkynes are among the oldest and the most studied reactions of organometallic chemistry :

The two most important insertion reactions of organo-transition compounds are those with CO and alkenes, the former into metal-carbon and the latter into metal-hydrogen, and they play significant roles in the catalytic processes. It may be emphasised here that the production of organic compounds from CO and H₂ (synthesis gas) will assume greater importance in future as the petroleum oil supplies dwindle. Organotransition metal complexes having chiral ligands have been increasingly used for asymmetric synthesis of organic compounds and the optical yields in these compounds are exceptionally high (90–100 percent). A large number of new chiral ligands have been designed and developed in recent years for this purpose³². Although homogeneous catalysts have several obvious advantages over conventional heterogeneous catalysts for industrial process, the former led to a number of practical problems such as corrosion, deposition of the catalyst on the walls of the reactor and recovery of the catalyst from the reaction products. To overcome these problems, polymer supported metal catalysts, which retain all the advantages, are being used for hydrogenation and hydrosilylation reactions. Some examples of these are Rh and Pd complexes of polystyrene with diphenylphosphine groups, Rh complex of polyacrylic acid, Rh and Pd complexes of polystyrene with iminodiacetic acid groups and Pd complexes of silicapolyorganosiloxanes.

Biological applications and environmental aspects:

The utility of organometallics in chemotherapy realised during the early part of this century has received continued attention. The discovery of vitamin-B₁₂ (containing a Co-C bond) created a renewed interest in bioorganometallic chemistry which has taken a new turn in recent years with the increasing awareness of the environmental aspects of metal-carbon bonded compounds. This problem is, in some cases, assuming serious dimensions in view of the large utilisation of organometallics as biocides and in various industries, calling for caution in the unrestricted use of materials like lead alkyls as oil additives for spark-ignition engines. Many countries have reduced or plan to reduce, organolead concentrations present in gasoline resulting in considerable reduction of the production of ethyl-lead as anti-knock compounds. In spite of an awareness of the problem for a long time, the environmental aspects of organometallics are just beginning to be unravelled, but much faster progress is expected. Following the first established cases (between 1953 and 1964) of Minnamata disease (methylmercury poisoning) in Japan, the use of organo-mercuric compounds as biocides have been banned in many countries as also the use of organotin as biocides and their use as stabilisers for polyvinyl chloride, particularly after the death of 102 persons in France in 1954 by the use of diethyltindiodide (known as stalinon). A concerted study by organometallic chemist and the biologists is imperative

in the use of such compounds and controlling the pollution.

Conclusion

Synthesis of new organometallic compounds may be undertaken in search of a desired property, to test theories of structure and chemical bonding, or as a result of an original concept of a new kind of structure. The products of this endeavour, in turn continue to open new lines of thought about chemical structure and to provide novel materials with useful and sometimes unexpected properties. The fascination for organometallic chemistry arises not only due to the tremendously varied chemistry and structure and bonding displayed by them, but also because of the actual and potential practical uses of such materials. It is a broad, interdisciplinary field that is not only of interest to organic and inorganic chemists, but also to physical chemists, chemical engineers, biologists, ecologists and environmentalists. It does provide unlimited challenges and opportunities in satisfying the societal needs. In order to realise these expectations, it is essential that the subject of organometallic chemistry may be treated as a real interdisciplinary subject which has far-reaching goals for not only the growth of knowledge but also for the development of industrial economy, for keeping the environment clean and for the synthesis of totally new materials of importance for national and economic security.

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